

EFFECT OF FLAKE ORIENTATION ANISOTROPY ON AGING AND DURABILITY OF GLASS/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *aging, durability, orientation anisotropy, glass flake, polymer composite*

1 Introduction

Polymers with flake reinforcement belong to a type of composite materials wherein the filler is two-dimensional, e.g. flakes, platelets, ribbons, disks, etc. These fillers are usually considered for planar structures due to their capability to reinforce in two dimensions [1]. The reinforcement of glass flakes into coatings and polymers provides physical enhancements such as improved barrier characteristics, dimensional stability, surface hardness, wear resistance, and mechanical stiffness.

The effectiveness of glass flake reinforcement in composite materials is dependent on the orientation of flakes inside the material matrix. For example, improved barrier properties are expected when flakes are oriented perpendicular rather than parallel to the diffusion direction. The flakes act as impermeable barriers and present a tortuous path for the diffusing environment [2]. This can delay the effects of environment exposure on the mechanical durability of these composite materials.

This paper presents the results of a study evaluating the effects of flake orientation anisotropy on the aging process and durability of glass/epoxy composites. The results are compared with data obtained from unfilled neat epoxy resins. The durability of composites is discussed in terms of their capability to retain their flexural properties during exposure to aging environment.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Untreated and silane-modified type E glass flakes were used as reinforcement. Bisphenol A type epoxy cured by methylene diamine was chosen as polymer

matrix. Specimens were prepared in accordance to Table 1 and have dimensions of 60 x 25 x 3 mm.

Table 1 Specification for flake epoxy composites

	Flake size [um]	Loading [vol. %]	Flake angle [deg.]	Silane coupling
A	600 x 5	7.6	0, 45, 90	X
B	600 x 5	16.7	0, 45, 90	X
C	600 x 5	16.7	0, 45, 90	O
D	420 x 5	16.7	0, 45, 90	X

Reinforcement angle of glass flakes were measured relative to specimen plane surface. Flake angles were induced in composites by applying several thin layers of glass flake-epoxy suspension on the mold surface plate by trowel. Then, after curing, the composite blocks were placed on a rotatable stage with a high-speed cutter located on top. The stage was then rotated at desired angles (0°, 45°, and 90°) for cutting of specimens with specific flake angle, as shown in Fig. 1. All specimens were oven-dried at 50°C for at least 100 hours before environment aging.

Fig. 1. Glass flakes oriented at an angle of 45° in C45 glass/epoxy composites

2.2 Environment aging

Specimens were immersed in deionized water maintained at 80°C. They were periodically removed from immersion, wiped with filter paper to remove excess liquid, and left in open air for 1 hour before weight was recorded. The percent weight change M_t was calculated using Eq. 1:

$$M_t = \frac{W_t - W_o}{W_o} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where W_t is the weight of the specimen at the given time of measurement and W_o is the original weight of the dry specimen.

2.3 Retention of flexural property

After measuring weight change, flexural modulus and strength of specimens were monitored during environment aging by performing three-point bending tests using Shimadzu Autograph AGS-1KNJ machine. Retention of flexural property RF was computed by Eq. 2:

$$RF = \frac{F_t}{F_o} \quad (2)$$

where F_t refers to the flexural modulus or strength of the specimen after specific time of immersion and F_o corresponds to the initial (or unaged) flexural property of the specimen.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Effect of aging on microstructure

Fig. 2 shows the specimen surface of sample A0 during environment aging in deionized water at 80°C using a stereomicroscope. The observed surface characteristics are almost the same with the other epoxy composite specimens during immersion. The evolution of contrasted marks in Fig. 1 signifies the formation of micro-sized cracks. The observed cavities are most likely due to osmosis, as seen in glass fiber – reinforced epoxy composites [3-4]. Epoxy and type E glass both contain water soluble components which dissolve in diffused water and create osmotic pressure differences between the resulting solutions and aging environment. Pressure pockets are then generated and make the specimens

porous. The observe pressure pockets are growing in size and in number while on exposure to aging environment and may form a penetrating percolated structure within the composite material.

Fig. 2. Specimen surface of sample A0 during moisture aging at 80°C.

3.2 Weight change during aging

Fig. 3 shows the weight change of epoxy resin and composites specimens during moisture aging at 80°C. The weight change behavior of epoxy resin under moisture aging indicates weight loss and leaching of soluble components [5] (for example, unreacted amine hardener) and polymer segments. Addition of glass flakes in epoxy resin delays weight loss and maintains material integrity. Compared to specimens with 45° and 90° flake angles, specimens with 0° flake angle (glass flakes oriented parallel to specimen plane surface or perpendicular to diffusion direction) have the lowest weight change during the initial exposure to moisture. At this flake orientation, the glass flakes reduces the diffusion area and increases the diffusion path length of water molecules during aging [2,6]. At higher angles, moisture diffusion during aging is fast and early initiation of weight loss is observed on specimens. It should be noted in Fig. 3 that compared to epoxy resin EP, composite specimens have higher weight

change due to the evolution of osmotic cracks inside the specimens which adds free volume to the material. Higher weight change of composite specimens than EP can also be attributed to wicking, or the preferred diffusion of water molecules at the glass/epoxy interface rather than at the bulk matrix. Increasing the volume fraction of glass flakes results to high concentration of weak interfaces and early initiation of weight loss, as shown when composites A and B are compared in Fig. 3. If the glass flakes are treated with silane coupling as with composite C, the initiation of weight loss is greatly delayed. Finally, if glass flakes of low aspect ratio are used like in composite D, early weight loss is observed due to low tortuosity and quick saturation of the composite specimens.

3.3 Effect of aging on flexural properties

Table 2 lists the initial flexural properties of neat resin and glass/epoxy composites before moisture aging. The addition of glass flakes greatly improves the flexural stiffness of epoxy resin at the cost of slight reduction in flexural strength. It is possible that the observed reduction in initial flexural strength can be due to incomplete wetting of glass flakes during preparation of composite specimens. At high volume fraction and low aspect ratio, the viscosity of flake-polymer suspension is high and mixing is difficult due to the tendency of flakes to aggregate. High concentration of flake-to-flake contacts in the cured composite may result to low efficiency of load transfer.

Table 2 Initial flexural properties of test samples

Specimen	Modulus [GPa]	Strength [MPa]
EP	2.5	91.5
A0	3.8	74.7
A45	3.3	76.4
A90	3.5	70.6
B0	4.5	75.5
B45	5.1	72.3
B90	5.8	78.4
C0	5.2	80.5
C45	4.9	79.6
C90	5.3	77.9
D0	5.1	63.4
D45	3.5	62.5
D90	3.9	60.9

Fig. 3. Weight change of neat epoxy and composites during moisture aging at 80°C

It can also be seen in Table 2 that silane coupling treatment of glass flakes in composite C slightly improves its flexural properties. Moreover, the

initial flexural properties of composites are somewhat unaffected by the orientation of glass flakes in the specimens.

Fig. 4. Retention of flexural modulus of neat epoxy and composites during moisture aging at 80°C

Fig. 5. Retention of flexural strength of neat epoxy and composites during moisture aging at 80°C

Figs. 4 and 5 show the retention of flexural modulus and strength of neat resin and glass/epoxy composites during moisture aging at 80°C, respectively. The observed gradual increase in flexural properties of neat resin and glass/epoxy composites after long exposure to moisture aging can be attributed to progression of cure and increased leaching of hydrolyzed polymer segments, resulting to network embrittlement [7]. Compared to neat resin EP, the lowest decrease in wet retention of flexural properties was observed in composites B and D, where wicking at the glass-epoxy interfaces dominates the flexural response of the composites. Aside from the weak interfaces and preferred moisture diffusion at these regions, osmotic cracks are also formed due to the soluble components of epoxy matrix and glass flakes. The evolving cracks, along with the weak interfaces, form a percolating structure that penetrates the composite material and contributes to less-efficient stress transfer between matrix and glass flakes. Improving the bond between glass flakes and epoxy matrix by silane coupling, as shown by the flexural response of composite C in Figs. 4 and 5, results to high wet retention and improved mechanical durability during aging.

The effect of flake orientation anisotropy on the flexural durability of the composites during moisture aging was observed to be somewhat limited only during the initial exposure. As shown by the flexural response of composites A and C before 200 h of immersion in Figs. 4 and 5, specimens with 0° flake angle have wet retention values higher than neat resin EP and specimens with 45° and 90° flake angles. At this stage of moisture aging, tortuosity induced by flake orientation governs the durability of the composite. The effect of such factor diminishes quickly as plasticization of bulk matrix due to moisture diffusion, wicking at the interface, and evolution of osmotic cracks continue to occur in glass/epoxy composites during aging.

4 Conclusion

The results show that the moisture aging process of glass/epoxy composites at 80°C depends strongly on the orientation of glass flakes induced on the material. Long initiation times of mass loss during moisture aging were observed for glass/epoxy composites with 0° flake angle and silane treatment. The influence of flake orientation anisotropy on the flexural durability of composites during moisture aging was found to be minimal and limited only during the initial exposure. Glass flakes modified with silane coupling gave higher wet retention of flexural properties than unmodified flakes.

Acknowledgement

The authors would like to specially thank the Hitachi Scholarship Foundation (HSF) for funding the oral presentation of this paper and Fuji Resin Co. Ltd. for the test samples.

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